

Robotic coverage path planning for ultrasonic inspection

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Abstract: Automatic robotic inspection of arbitrary free-form shapes is relevant for many quality control applications in different industries. We propose a method for planning the motion of an industrial robot to perform ultrasonic inspection of varying 3D shapes. Our method starts with the calculation of a set of sub-paths. These sub-paths are derived from streamlines. The underlying vector field is deduced from local curvature of the inspected geometry. Intermediate robot motions are planned to connect individual sub-paths to get a single complete inspection path. Coverage is calculated via ray tracing to simulate the propagation of ultrasound signals. This simulation enables the algorithm to proceed adaptively and to find a good trade-off between path length and coverage. We report experiments for four different geometries. Results indicate that shorter paths are achieved by using ray tracing for adaptive adjustment of streamline density. Our algorithm is tailored to ultrasonic inspection. However, the main concept of exploiting local surface curvature and streamlines for coverage path planning generalizes to other robotic inspection problems.

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1. Introduction

Coverage path planning (CPP) deals with the problem of finding a path for a robot to cover some region of interest. Depending on the application, coverage may relate to visiting, inspecting, or anyhow treating (mowing, painting, etc.) the complete region. Hence, the definition of what region is covered by which robot configuration or position strongly depends on the application. For example, the region covered by a lawn mower robot at a specific position is a disk-shaped area around the center point of the rotating blade. For a robot performing optical inspection, the covered area is derived from the camera position, the field of view, and obstacles within the field of view. In any case, the definition of coverage is an important topic for all coverage planning algorithms.

We introduce a method for coverage path planning that is built upon a heuristic based on streamlines. Our main application is robotic inspection via ultrasonic testing (UT). In order to calculate coverage, we rely on a ray tracing approach. Via ray tracing it is possible to generate a volumetric representation of covered regions inside the inspected part. While the ray tracing approach is very specific to UT, the heuristic of using streamlines is applicable to other coverage planning problems.

This article is structured in the following way. In section 2 we review related work on coverage path planning and coverage calculation. In section 3 we provide an overview about streamlines in general. To derive streamlines for our CPP algorithm, we build upon a vector field defined by local surface curvature. Surface curvature is discussed in section 4. Another building block for our method is ray tracing to simulate propagation of ultrasound waves - outlined in section 5. Section 6 explains how we put

39 everything together for the proposed coverage path planning algorithm. An evaluation
40 of the algorithm is provided in section 7 and conclusions are drawn in section 8.

41 2. Related Work

42 Most existing work on coverage path planning relates to problems where a robot
43 moves in 2D space. This is interesting for applications such as lawn mowers, vacuum
44 robots, and harvesting machines. In literature, recent surveys on coverage path plan-
45 ning have limited focus on 3D coverage [1,2]. Many classical approaches like cellular
46 decomposition [3], grid-based [4], and graph-based [5] methods are difficult to extend
47 to 3D cases. In general, computational complexity tends to increase massively with the
48 transition from 2D to 3D.

49 Many coverage planning algorithms address the problem of a mobile robot that is
50 required to visit all locations in the region of interest. The region of interest is discretized
51 so that it is represented by a finite number of points or grid elements [6,7]. Depending
52 on the application, additionally the orientation of inspection positions needs to be con-
53 sidered. This enlarges the space of possible solutions leading to increased computational
54 complexity. For on-machine inspection with a 5-axis system, a method was proposed
55 that considers multiple orientations per inspected point [8]. Subsequently, the points
56 with different orientations are connected by solving a traveling salesman problem.

57 Robotic inspection using ultrasound is relevant for multiple quality control appli-
58 cations in industry. An example for robotic UT is the inspection of components of a
59 thermonuclear reactor [9]. Even in the medical field, ultrasonic scanning by a robot is an
60 interesting topic. A recent method [10] is based on force-feedback during the scanning
61 process.

62 In the context of robotic scanning, recent work involves in-line dimensional in-
63 spection via Spatio-Temporal Adaptive Sampling (STAS) [11]. This method estimates
64 deviations of the whole part based on partial measurement of a free form surface. In
65 addition, the method adaptively selects the next region to be measured in each step. An
66 interesting extension of coverage path planning deals with multi-robot environments
67 [12,13]. For most applications this requires some kind of synchronization of robots. Al-
68 though there could be some potential of using our method in a multi-robot environment,
69 we do not further address this scenario.

70 As computational complexity is often high in the context of 3D surface inspection,
71 some papers propose heuristics that iteratively grow the inspected region. One method
72 uses a geometric random tree to sample possible future configurations [14]. This was
73 shown to provide good scaling properties with respect to the complexity of scenarios. In
74 general, the concept of iteratively growing the covered area with influence from control
75 theory is referred to as *receding horizon*. A recent work [15] deploys this concept for online
76 path planning to adaptively acquire information from the surface. Information already
77 acquired is inserted into a manifold Gaussian process and influences the progressive
78 calculation of the path.

79 A problem that is related to coverage path planning is classical point-to-point robot
80 path planning. Robot path planning addresses the problem of finding a valid sequence
81 of configurations or states by which a robot moves from some start position to a target
82 position. Depending on the space of possible states, this can have different levels of
83 complexity. There are well-known algorithms available, e.g. rapidly exploring random
84 trees (RRT) [16]), that solve the point-to-point path planning problem. In the following,
85 we deploy standard solutions for point-to-point robot motion planning. This is mainly
86 relevant for situations where sub-paths that cover separate regions need to be connected.
87 The main intention of such a connecting motion is not to increase coverage but to perform
88 a transition from one region or robot configuration to another.

89 An adequate definition of coverage is an important topic for CPP algorithms.
90 Definitions of coverage can be very diverse ranging from point-wise coverage [12]
91 to drones that spray disinfectants [17]. In the present work we focus on volumetric

92 ultrasonic inspection. The respective coverage relates to the propagation of ultrasound
 93 waves through the investigated materials. We deploy ray tracing to approximate the
 94 process of ultrasonic inspection. The goal is to predict the volumetric coverage for a
 95 single sensor position.

96 In order to model inspection via UT, it is necessary to have a closer look at the
 97 underlying physical process. For ultrasonic inspection, phased arrays are commonly
 98 used for signal generation and data acquisition. The Total Focusing Method (TFM) -
 99 introduced in [18] - is thereby one of the most popular methods. The term refers to a
 100 post-processing of the full matrix capture which accounts for all received signals of all
 101 receiver-sender pairs of the phased array. In order to calculate volumetric coverage for a
 102 single sensor position, we need to approximate how ultrasonic waves propagate from a
 103 specific sender to a specific receiver interacting with the specimen.

104 Generally, strategies for numerically evaluating sound propagation can be grouped
 105 into wave-based and geometric based approaches: The underlying wave equation can
 106 be solved by classical methods, e.g. the finite element method and boundary element
 107 method [19,20]. This is especially useful to evaluate low frequency effects like diffraction.
 108 A geometric acoustic approach on the other hand is suitable for high frequency waves, i.e.
 109 if the examined wave lengths are short in relation to the objects the wave is interacting
 110 with. In order to additionally account for low frequency effects, geometric and wave
 111 based approaches can be combined [21].

112 For our purpose, we use a geometric approach, which already is a widely studied
 113 field, motivated by a variety of use cases, e.g. auralization for audio post processing and
 114 virtual environments or simulation of classrooms helping the design process [19,22,23].
 115 Recently, realistic ultrasound rendering was studied to enhance medical training [24–27].

116 3. Streamlines

117 Physical flow, for example fluid flow in a liquid, is described by a vector field. If the
 118 vector field does not change over time, we call it a static vector field. The trajectory of a
 119 very light particle (with zero-mass) through the flow follows a streamline. Given a start
 120 point and a vector field, it is possible to calculate the respective streamline. The position
 121 of the particle evolves through the vector field such that the velocity of the particle in
 122 each point corresponds to the value of the vector field at that position. For a vector field
 123 \mathbf{v} , a streamline $\mathbf{s}_t = \mathbf{s}_t(t)$ is defined as

$$\frac{d\mathbf{s}_t}{dt} \times \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{s}_t) = 0 \quad (1)$$

124 where t is the parameter of the streamline. In general, at any point along the
 125 streamline \mathbf{s}_t the vector $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{s}_t)$ is parallel or anti-parallel to the derivative $\frac{d\mathbf{s}_t}{dt}$. Therefore,
 126 both vectors differ at most in their absolute size:

$$\frac{ds_x}{dv_x} = \frac{ds_y}{dv_y} = \frac{ds_z}{dv_z} \quad (2)$$

127 where $\mathbf{s}_t = (s_x, s_y, s_z)^T$ and $\mathbf{v} = (v_x, v_y, v_z)^T$. The streamline is not defined where
 128 the vector field is zero. Figure 1 shows an example for a streamline in 2D. The first
 129 step for calculation of a streamline is to select a seed point. At this point, the respective
 130 vector from the vector field is investigated. Via numerical integration, the streamline is
 131 expanded point by point following the parallel and anti-parallel direction of the vector
 132 field in each point. In the following sections we outline how streamlines are used as a
 133 basis for the trajectory of a sensor and the corresponding robot path.

Figure 1. Example of a streamline and its corresponding vector field in 2d. The selected seed point is shown in the center of the figure.

134 4. Using curvature as vector field

135 Any twice differentiable parametric surface S in R^3 has two principal curvatures κ_1
 136 and κ_2 at each surface point. These principal curvatures correspond to two perpendicular
 137 vector \mathbf{t}_1 and \mathbf{t}_2 in the tangent plane. Given a parametric surface description, the
 138 respective tangent vectors of principal curvatures can be derived analytically. In case
 139 of discretized surface representations, e.g. triangle meshes, principal curvature tangent
 140 vectors need to be approximated numerically.

141 Different methods were proposed to calculate curvature for arbitrary surfaces. For
 142 example, one approach builds upon Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of points
 143 in the local neighborhood [28]. We follow a similar approach. However, instead of an
 144 analysis of points, we estimate curvature based on surface normals. A Singular Value
 145 Decomposition (SVD) of surface normals delivers curvatures κ_i and tangent vectors \mathbf{t}_i .

Figure 2. Surface normal \mathbf{n} (blue arrow), tangent to first principal curvature \mathbf{t}_1 (green arrow) and second principal curvature \mathbf{t}_2 (red arrow) form an orthogonal system. The box shown above the surface s represents a line-shaped sensor. For linear phased array ultrasound we claim that the long edge of the sensor should be parallel to the maximum curvature.

146 The goal of our CPP algorithm is to keep a suitable alignment of a line-shaped
147 linear phased array ultrasound sensor relative to the surface of the inspected part. We
148 assume that suitable poses along the path can be derived from local surface properties,
149 i.e. orientations of the principal curvatures. For ultrasonic inspection with a linear
150 phased array it is important that a large fraction of the complete energy of the emitted
151 signal is also reflected back to the transducer head. Ideally, the surface normals of all
152 points at which reflection occurs point towards the phased array. Small variations (e.g.
153 due to calibration errors or positioning inaccuracies) within the plane ϵ spanned by the
154 surface normal \mathbf{n} and \mathbf{t}_1 lead to only moderate loss of reflected signal intensity. If the
155 variation is small enough, there is still a chance that the reflection hits an element from
156 the phased array. Surface normals that are tilted out of this plane result in high loss of
157 signal intensity. The reason for this is that reflections that exit the plane are not captured
158 by any of the phased array transducer elements.

159 5. Ray-Tracing based Process Model

160 We propose to estimate the coverage of a linear phased array ultrasound sensor via
161 ray-tracing. This provides a good tradeoff between physical accuracy and computational
162 complexity. The main goal is to predict at which locations defects are detectable.

163 Common defects in carbon fiber re-inforced plastic (CFRP) parts are delaminations
164 and porosities [29]. These fault types cause two different effects on the captured ultra-
165 sound data which are utilized for fault detection: (a) delaminations cause reflections of
166 the sound (b) porosities scatter the signal and therefore cause an attenuation of the back
167 wall echo. We use a ray tracing approach to judge if both fault types can be detected in a
168 volume element from a given sensor pose (position and orientation). For each sensor
169 element of the phased array, we simulate the propagation of the wave vector. If a ray
170 passes a specific volume element (of the discretized specimen) we assume that delami-
171 nations can be detected. If the same ray is reflected at the back wall of the specimen and
172 afterwards detected by the sensor we assume that an existing porosity in that volume
173 element could be detected by detecting a back wall attenuation. Volume elements that
174 are passed by rays that meet these criteria are marked as captured, see Figure 3.

Figure 3. Illustration of coverage calculation via ray tracing. Two rays that are emitted by the sensor are shown. At any surface, transmission and reflection occur. Hence, each ray spans a tree. Voxels that are traversed by rays are shown in color. Red voxels correspond to a tree of rays that do not return to the sensor - at least not within the first four levels of the tree. Blue voxels are covered by rays that return back to the sensor. In contrast to red voxels, we consider blue voxels to be covered.

175 The ultrasound sensor used throughout this paper is a linear phased array (PA)
176 that consists of 64 transducers and has a width of 124 mm. The sensor is modeled as a

177 rectangle where the single transducers are spaced equidistantly along the longest edge
178 of the sensor. Rays are emitted at the center of each transducer in a range of different
179 angles with a pre-configured maximal aperture. The number of rays per transducer is
180 fixed. Ray tracing is performed with a recursion depth of 4. All rays that are reflected by
181 the geometry in such a way that they hit a phased array element are marked as captured
182 by the sensor. As illustrated in Figure 4, the modeled PA sensor is placed at a given
183 working distance relative to a streamline that is calculated for the mesh surface. Emitted
184 rays and reflections/transmissions are shown. Only rays emitted near the center of the
185 PA sensor are cast back to the sensor, due to the challenging position of the sensor.

Figure 4. Visualization of reflected rays on the geometry of a complex beam. The PA sensor is positioned at a working distance to a streamline that follows the edge of the part. To reduce clutter in the visualization, the depicted phased array sensor consists of only 21 transducers. Only 5 co-planar rays are emitted by each transducer. The rays highlighted in orange are emitted by the same transducer near the center of the ultrasound sensor. Some rays are reflected at the front wall and some at the back wall of the specimen.

186 6. Coverage Path Planning

187 A conventional approach for coverage path planning is to move the sensor over the
188 surface along a set of evenly spaced parallel lines. Those lines are often traversed in such
189 a way that a meander-shaped path is formed. However, by more accurate modelling of
190 the inspection process it is possible to generate shorter inspection paths as the distance
191 between scan lines can be chosen according to the local specimen's geometry (e.g. flat
192 regions allow larger gaps between scan lines because the sensor is able to capture a larger
193 region at once). To achieve a more reasonable placement of scan lines, we formulate a
194 process model which addresses both, the problem of (a) mapping surface points to sensor
195 orientations and positions and (b) determining the inspected volume of the specimen for
196 a certain sensor pose.

197 When determining the sensor pose for a given point on the surface, the following
198 constraints need to be considered:

- 199 1. To maximize the signal strength, the sensor has to be placed such that the main
200 direction of emission (the sensor's z-axis) is parallel to the surface normal and the
201 center of the sensor is positioned along that normal.
- 202 2. The inspection distance should be equal to the optimal working distance of the
203 sensor.
- 204 3. To maximize coverage, the long edge of the sensor (the sensor's y-axis) has to be
205 perpendicular to the scanning direction. That is, the sensor needs to be positioned
206 as show in Figure 4 where the phased array travels along the streamline which is
207 depicted as a black line on the mesh surface.

208 4. For every point of a curved surface, the sensor should be orientated such that the
 209 direction of the largest curvature is parallel to the sensor's y-axis. This tends to
 210 maximize the strength of captured signals.

211 Note that the PA sensor is invariant under a 180° rotation around its z-axis. Thus, for
 212 every point on a curved surface we can consider the sensor pose as fully defined by the
 213 aforementioned constraints.

214 Our coverage path planning approach can be divided into two separate phases:
 215 (a) a Cartesian coverage path planning phase, see Algorithm 1 that uses the described
 216 process model and (b) a greedy search to derive a robot path that scans each point on the
 217 Cartesian path exactly once while considering the limitations of the robot kinematics.
 218 The Cartesian coverage path planning algorithm uses the specimen's CAD data to plan
 219 a path on the outer surface of the specimen. To keep track of the inspected volume, the
 220 algorithm simulates the ultrasonic data acquisition. The volumetric information is then
 221 projected back onto the surface. This allows to generate a coverage path that includes
 222 information about actual covered volume.

223 The complete algorithm proceeds as follows. Initially, the input mesh is voxelized
 224 and the outer surface is discretized. For the discretized surface the vector field based
 225 on curvature is calculated, and all surface points are initially marked as seed points.
 226 Afterwards, the algorithm iterates over all seed points in descending order of their
 227 curvature value. For each seed point a streamline which follows the second principal
 228 curvature is expanded. Once the streamline expansion is terminated the volumetric
 229 inspection is updated by running the ray tracing algorithm for every point on the
 230 streamline. Seed points are skipped if all voxels along the surface-normal (inward) are
 231 already inspected or if another streamline is in close proximity.

Algorithm 1 Cartesian coverage path planning algorithm

```

1: procedure CCPP( MESH )
2:   voxelgrid  $\leftarrow$  voxelize mesh ▷ mark all voxels as not inspected
3:   surface  $\leftarrow$  discretize outer surface
4:   seeds  $\leftarrow$  calculate curvature vector field for surface
5:   sort seeds using the curvature value in descending order
6:   for s in seeds do
7:     if s is too close to an existing streamline then
8:       skip s
9:     if curvature of s  $>$  threshold then
10:      streamline  $\leftarrow$  expand streamline from s
11:    else ▷ Note: specimen is now subdivided into flat areas
12:      A  $\leftarrow$  connected flat area containing s
13:      c  $\leftarrow$  center of A, re-projected onto the mesh
14:      v  $\leftarrow$  vector pointing along the principal component of A
15:      streamline  $\leftarrow$  expand streamline from c with initial direction v
16:    for p in streamline do
17:      inspected voxels  $\leftarrow$  run ray-tracing algorithm for pose p
18:      update voxelgrid using inspected voxel
19:    for s in seeds do ▷ Only the seed points underneath the sensor are considered
20:      n  $\leftarrow$  #voxels along the surface-normal marked as not inspected
21:      if n = 0 then
22:        remove s

```

232 If a seed point's curvature value is below a given threshold, the corresponding area
 233 is considered flat. Note that once a seed point meets this criterion the not inspected
 234 area of the mesh is composed of unconnected flat areas. On flat areas streamlines are
 235 expanded in a straight line from the areas center along its principal component.

236 Once the Cartesian paths are created, the second phase of the algorithm is executed.
 237 We deploy a greedy search algorithm that generates the corresponding robot path. In a

238 first step the algorithm calculates multiple valid robot paths per streamline. In a second
239 step the separate streamline-paths are connected, yielding the final robot path that covers
240 all points on the Cartesian paths exactly once.

241 For a six axis robot each Cartesian pose may have multiple inverse kinematics (IK)
242 solutions - i.e. multiple joint configurations yield the same sensor pose. To generate valid
243 robot paths for a given streamline first all possible joint configurations are calculated
244 for each point on the streamline. Since the sensor is invariant under a 180° rotation
245 around its z-axis, also the IK solutions for the rotated pose are calculated. In a next step
246 *connectable* IK solutions for adjacent points on the streamline are connected forming robot
247 path segments that the robot can traverse without considerable re-configuration. More
248 precisely, two points a and b (in joint space) are *connectable*, if the Cartesian midpoint
249 $m = (FK(b) - FK(a))/2$ and the point obtained from the forward kinematics (FK) of the
250 midpoint in $m' = FK((b - a)/2)$ are sufficiently close in joint space. The path segments
251 are constructed in such a way that multiple *streamline paths* are generated. A streamline
252 path consists of multiple path segments which together cover all points of the streamline
253 exactly once. Note that a path segment may be part of multiple streamline paths.

254 In the final stage of the algorithm the generated path segments are connected.
255 Starting from a randomly selected path segment, the final complete robot path is created.
256 In each iteration the path is expanded at one of its endpoints by the path segment which
257 is closest in joint-space. Once a path segment is used, all other path segments covering
258 the same streamline that do not share a streamline path are deleted. This guarantees that
259 all points of the Cartesian paths are inspected exactly once.

260 7. Results

261 To determine the effectiveness of the proposed method, we evaluate it on different
262 geometries. Our evaluation focuses on the Cartesian path planning phase, or more
263 precisely, on the method used to mark a part of the surface as inspected. The algorithm
264 proposed in section 6 (later called *papp-adaptive*) iteratively generates streamlines and
265 deploys a ray tracing algorithm after each iteration. The obtained volumetric inspection
266 is then projected back onto the surface, marking surface points that are above a column
267 of fully inspected voxels as inspected. This approach is compared to a baseline algorithm
268 (*papp-base-d*) that does not consider the volumetric inspection, but simply considers
269 surface points in a certain proximity d to the streamline as inspected. Four different
270 values for d were tested: 30 mm, 40 mm, 50 mm and 60 mm. The phased array sensor
271 has a width of 114 mm, thus, an inspection radius of 60 mm still yields good results on
272 slightly curved surfaces.

273 The algorithm variants are compared using the Cartesian path length, i.e. the total
274 length of all streamlines. The quality of the path is measured as the percentage of the
275 (voxelized) mesh-volume that is covered by the given path. For the baseline algorithm
276 the ray tracing algorithm is used to derive the volumetric inspection once all streamlines
277 are calculated.

278 The evaluation is conducted using four mesh objects shown in figure 5. These
279 objects are: WAVE: a moderately wavy plate with increasing wall thickness, EDGE1:
280 an edge which is bent at its center with thinner walls towards the ends, EDGE2: an
281 edge that bends twice in two different directions and BEAM: a complex U-shaped beam.
282 Surface curvature has a big impact on the size of the inspected volume. A large fraction
283 of energy is lost when the surface normal is not parallel to the sensors z-axis. Challenging
284 areas are also those with thick walls and/or non-parallel back walls. The wall thickness
285 for all objects is in a range between 15 mm to 55 mm. All mesh objects are available
286 online¹. Streamlines calculated in the first phase of the coverage planning algorithm
287 *papp-adaptive* are illustrated in figure 5.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/5173521#.YRIJECxVPY>

(a) WAVE: Waved plate

(b) EDGE1: Edge with one bend

(c) EDGE2: Edge with two bends

(d) BEAM: Complex U-shaped beam

Figure 5. Test objects used to evaluate the proposed algorithm. The streamlines (in red) are generated with the following variants of the algorithm (from top-left to bottom-right): papp-base-60, papp-adaptive, papp-base-40, papp-adaptive

Mesh	Algorithm	Path length ([mm])	Coverage (%)	Missed voxels
WAVE	papp-adaptive	2048.0	100	0
	papp-base-30	3985.0	100	0
	papp-base-40	2009.0	100	0
	papp-base-50	2005.0	100	0
	papp-base-60	2006.0	100	0
EDGE1	papp-adaptive	3985.9	100	0
	papp-base-30	4816.8	99.99	3
	papp-base-40	3226.9	99.98	7
	papp-base-50	3142.9	99.76	82
	papp-base-60	2441.9	99.52	163
EDGE2	papp-adaptive	6906.4	100	0
	papp-base-30	8835.8	100	0
	papp-base-40	7147.8	99.96	37
	papp-base-50	5628.5	99.96	34
	papp-base-60	4723.8	99.92	71
BEAM	papp-adaptive	1753.8	100	0
	papp-base-30	1558.0	100	0
	papp-base-40	1133.0	98.13	124
	papp-base-50	739.9	80.01	1329

Table 1: Comparison of different Cartesian path planning algorithms for four different mesh objects. The path length is the combined Cartesian path length in millimeters. The coverage indicates the percentage of voxels that are inspected using the generated path. The last column states the total number of missed voxels.

288 Table 1 shows the path length and achieved coverage for the different algorithms.
 289 For flat areas, such as the object depicted in Figure 5a, the baseline algorithms achieve
 290 full coverage with short paths. However, for more challenging areas, e.g. for the highly
 291 curved center area on the mesh EDGE1, the baseline algorithms require an even smaller

inspection radius to achieve full coverage. Figure 6 visualizes the voxels that are missed
by algorithm `papp-base-60`.

Table 1 summarizes path length and coverage for different versions of our algorithm on the four different test geometries. The `papp-adaptive` version of the algorithm performs quite well in the sense that it delivers full coverage for all test geometries. For WAVE there is little advantage of using the adaptive method as the respective geometry contains only moderate curvature. For EDGE1 and EDGE2 the adaptive method outperforms all other variants of the algorithm. For these geometries `papp-adaptive` delivers full coverage with shorter path length. For BEAM the two algorithm variants `papp-adaptive` and `papp-base-30` both achieve full coverage. However, in this case the `papp-adaptive` version requires a slightly larger path length than `papp-base-30`.

Figure 6. Visualization of the 163 missed voxels on the mesh EDGE1 for the path planned using `papp-base-60`.

8. Conclusions and future work

Coverage path planning for inspection of complex 3D geometries is a challenging task. The exact solution of this problem is computationally not feasible. In this paper we presented an approach that builds upon a heuristic using streamlines. Local curvature is taken as the measure to evolve individual streamlines. An important parameter of our algorithm is the distance at which streamlines are placed. This can either be a fixed value or can be adjusted adaptively. In the latter case, coverage is approximated via ray tracing in order to estimate the actual coverage for a path. While ray tracing is a relatively simple method to simulate ultrasound propagation it provides a good trade-off between physical correctness and computational effort. An evaluation on four selected geometries shows that adaptive distances of streamlines can bring an improvement in the range of 17 to 22 percent shorter path length with the same or even better coverage on non-flat geometries. While the method does not provide an optimal solution to the computationally intractable coverage path planning problem, our method is well suited to many practical robotic ultrasonic scanning problems. Moreover, the method of using streamlines lends itself well for adaptation of similar inspection tasks.

Future work will cover topics related to improvements of the ray tracing algorithm for better coverage calculation. Specifically, we plan to compare the calculated coverage with real ultrasound scans.

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References

- Galceran, E.; Carreras, M. A survey on coverage path planning for robotics. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems* **2013**, *61*, 1258–1276. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.robot.2013.09.004>.
- Bormann, R.; Jordan, F.; Hampp, J.; Hägele, M. Indoor Coverage Path Planning: Survey, Implementation, Analysis. 2018 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA), 2018, pp. 1718–1725. doi:10.1109/ICRA.2018.8460566.

3. Oksanen, T.; Visala, A. Coverage path planning algorithms for agricultural field machines. *Journal of Field Robotics* **2009**, *26*, 651–658.
4. Gabriely, Y.; Rimón, E. Spiral-STC: an on-line coverage algorithm of grid environments by a mobile robot. *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, 2002, Vol. 1, pp. 954–960. doi:10.1109/ROBOT.2002.1013479.
5. Li, B.; Feng, P.; Zeng, L.; Xu, C.; Zhang, J. Path planning method for on-machine inspection of aerospace structures based on adjacent feature graph. *Computer-Integrated Manufacturing* **2017**, *54*, 17–34.
6. Gajjar, S.; Bhadani, J.; Dutta, P.; Rastogi, N. Complete coverage path planning algorithm for known 2d environment. 2017 2nd IEEE International Conference on Recent Trends in Electronics, Information Communication Technology (RTEICT), 2017, pp. 963–967. doi:10.1109/RTEICT.2017.8256741.
7. Glorieux, E.; Franciosa, P.; Ceglarek, D. Coverage path planning with targetted viewpoint sampling for robotic free-form surface inspection. *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing* **2020**, *61*, 101843. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcim.2019.101843.
8. Yamin, L.; Zeng, L.; Tang, K. Orientation-point relation based inspection path planning method for 5-axis OMI system. *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing* **2019**. doi:10.1016/j.rcim.2019.101827.
9. Bulavinov, A.; R., P.; Gurieva, T.; Lyanzberg, D.; Lider, A.; Demyanuk, D.; Sernev, D.; Zhvyrblya, V. Robot-based In-Process Examination of ITER Dome and First-Wall Panels based on Novel Ultrasonic Tomography Approach. 19th World Conference on Non-Destructive Testing, 2016.
10. Chen, S.; Li, Z.; Lin, Y.; Wang, F.; Cao, Q. Automatic ultrasound scanning robotic system with optical waveguide-based force measurement. *International Journal of Computer Assisted Radiology and Surgery* **2021**, *16*, 1015–1025.
11. Babu, M.; Franciosa, P.; Ceglarek, D. Spatio-temporal adaptive sampling for effective coverage measurement planning during quality inspection of free form surfaces using robotic 3d optical scanner. *Manufacturing Systems* **2019**.
12. Collins, L.; Ghassemi, P.; Esfahani, E.T.; Doermann, D.; Dantu, K.; Chowdhury, S. Scalable Coverage Path Planning of Multi-Robot Teams for Monitoring Non-Convex Areas, 2021, [arXiv:cs.RO/2103.14709].
13. Dai, P.; Hassan, M.; Sun, S.; Zhang, M.; Bian, Z.; Liu, D. A framework for multi-robot coverage analysis of large and complex structures. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing* **2021**. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/s10845-021-01745-8.
14. Birchner, A.; Kamel, M.; Alexis, K.; Oleynikova, H.; Siegwart, R. Receding horizon path planning for 3D exploration and surface inspection. *Autonomous Robots* **2016**, *42*, 291–306.
15. Zhu, H.; Chung, J.J.; Lawrance, N.R.J.; Siegwart, R.; Alonso-Mora, J. Online Informative Path Planning for Active Information Gathering of a 3D Surface, 2021, [arXiv:cs.RO/2103.09556].
16. Kuffner, J.; LaValle, S. RRT-connect: An efficient approach to single-query path planning. *Proceedings 2000 ICRA. Millennium Conference. IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation. Symposia Proceedings (Cat. No.00CH37065)*, 2000, Vol. 2, pp. 995–1001 vol.2. doi:10.1109/ROBOT.2000.844730.
17. Vazquez-Carmona, E.V.; Vasquez-Gomez, J.I.; Lozada, J.C.H.; Antonio-Cruz, M. Coverage Path Planning for Spraying Drones, 2021, [arXiv:cs.RO/2105.08743].
18. Holmes, C.; Drinkwater, B.; Wilcox, P. Post-processing of the full matrix of ultrasonic transmit-receive array data for non-destructive evaluation. *NDT and E International* **2005**, *38*, 701–711. Publisher: Elsevier Other: in press, doi:10.1016/j.ndteint.2005.04.002.
19. Lakka, E.; Malamos, A.G.; Pavlakis, K.G.; Ware, J.A. Spatial Sound Rendering—A Survey. *IJIMAI* **2018**, *5*, 33–45.
20. Leckey, C.A.; Parker, F.R. NDE and SHM simulation for CFRP composites. *Proc. of American Society for Composites 29th Technical Conference*, 2014, Vol. 454.
21. Rabenstein, R.; Schips, O.; Stenger, A. Acoustic rendering of buildings. 5th Int. IBPSA Conference Building Simulation. Citeseer, 1997, Vol. 2, pp. 181–188.
22. Hulusic, V.; Harvey, C.; Debattista, K.; Tsingos, N.; Walker, S.; Howard, D.; Chalmers, A. Acoustic rendering and auditory–visual cross-modal perception and interaction. *Computer Graphics Forum. Wiley Online Library*, 2012, Vol. 31, pp. 102–131.
23. Röber, N.; Kaminski, U.; Masuch, M. Ray acoustics using computer graphics technology. 10th International Conference on Digital Audio Effects (DAFx-07), S. Citeseer, 2007, pp. 117–124.
24. Mattausch, O.; Goksel, O. Monte-Carlo Ray-Tracing for Realistic Interactive Ultrasound Simulation. 6th Eurographics Workshop on Visual Computing for Biology and Medicine, held in conjunction with the 10th Conference in Medical Imaging and Visualization, VCBM/MedViz 2016, Bergen, Norway, September 7-9, 2016. Eurographics Association, 2016, pp. 173–181. doi:10.2312/vcbm.20161285.
25. Mattausch, O.; Makhinya, M.; Goksel, O. Realistic Ultrasound Simulation of Complex Surface Models Using Interactive Monte-Carlo Path Tracing. *Computer Graphics Forum. Wiley Online Library*, 2018, Vol. 37, pp. 202–213.
26. Østergaard, M.L.; Nielsen, K.R.; Albrecht-Beste, E.; Ersbøll, A.K.; Konge, L.; Nielsen, M.B. Simulator training improves ultrasound scanning performance on patients: a randomized controlled trial. *European radiology* **2019**, *29*, 3210–3218.
27. Yeo, L.; Romero, R. Optical ultrasound simulation-based training in obstetric sonography. *The Journal of Maternal-Fetal & Neonatal Medicine* **2020**, pp. 1–16.
28. Yang, Y.L.; Lai, Y.K.; Hu, S.M.; Pottmann, H. Robust Principal Curvatures on Multiple Scales. SGP 2006: 4th Eurographics Symposium on Geometry processing; Polthier, K.; Sheffer, A., Eds. Eurographics Association, 2006, pp. 223–226.
29. Hodgkinson, J. *Mechanical Testing of Advanced Fibre Composites*; 2000; pp. 175–176. doi:10.1201/9781439822791.